

THE ARTISTIC FUNCTION OF THE “WAY” IMAGE IN CHOLPON’S WORKS

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Annotation: This article discusses the image of the road in the work of Cholpon. The researcher analyzed the artistic expression of mental and psychological processes in the poet's lyrics. There were made certain generalizations about Cholpon's ability to create an image through the analysis of many lyrical poems in the article.

Keywords: lyrics, genre, spiritual experience, image, symbol, lyrical "I", poetic skill.

As a talented poet, skillful writer, mature translator and publicist, one of the creators who made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature is Abdulhamid Sulayman's son Cholpon. Along with many poetic images, the image of the road is widely used in Cholpon's prose and poetry. His creative legacy includes publicist works such as "Among the Ruins", "Letters from Shymkent" and the travelogue "Memories of the Road" [Cholpon. Works. 3 volumes. J.2] belonging to the genre of road memoirs. Since these works are not only educationally valuable, but are directed to feelings and experiences, they "inform the reader about the spiritual and psychological experiences of the creator in a certain period" [Yakubov

I. 90 pp.].

In his travelogue "Memories of the Road" consisting of eight sections, prose and poetry are harmoniously combined. The writer's information and comments - the sincere pains of the creator are expressed in a lyric-epic way in the travelogue,.

Literary critic D. Kuronov, while thinking about the writer's travelogue "Yol esdaligii" (Memories of the Road), dwells on the images of the road and the traveler in it, and says: "Of course, spatial and periodic changes have a certain impact on the traveler's mentality and outlook. The proverb of our sages "Walking is a river, sitting is a mat" is not in vain named. Perhaps because of this, characters who are shown growing up and changing in oral and written literature often go on a journey. In Cholpon's creativity, the image of the road often serves to make similar internal comparisons. [Kuronov D. About the meaning layer in "Memories of the Road". 159 pp.].

In this travelogue, Cholpon describes how the mountains, which look beautiful from afar, become more and more beautiful as they get closer, and says that they are as "beautiful as his love", "as big as his fear". It was not in vain. Cholpon urges us to focus on the fact that his pain can only be understood by getting closer to his soul, and that in the process his sense of fear has grown.

Cholpon realized that his dreams were blocked by real facts. He hesitates, not knowing what is the force blocking the rise of the mountain. In our opinion, special attention should be paid to this situation. Cholpon, who could not find an answer to the rise of the mountain, sought the answer to his question from nature, although intuitively, he sought to know finite objects, thereby understanding the secrets of infinity. Because when you want to climb to imaginary heights, and climb to the point where the eyes are playing, the mountains also stop growing.

In this travelogue, the writer describes the surroundings while walking on the road, but at the same time the road comes as both an image and a poetic device. After

all, as the literary critic G. Ernazarova said: "... the concept of a road in fiction has always carried a symbolic and metaphorical meaning as a person's "life path", "entering a new path", "historical path" [Ernazarova G.74 p.] Also, the scientist observes the meeting of different poetic interpretations of the "road" both in the prose and poetry of Cholpon. "For example, in the lyrical digressions in the travelogue "Memory of the Road", the poet achieves a unique poetic goal by combining symbolic lyrics with Eastern Sufi literature to illuminate the process of finding his goals, mental anguish, and identity."

In Cholpon's poems "My Ways", "My musical instrument", "Way of love", "Way of motherland", "On great way", "Leave me alone", "The Desire to Take Comfort", "Love of Eremite" and "Beautiful" the image of the road is written with a different purpose.

The image of the road used in Cholpan's poems is "interpreted as a symbol of the struggle for national liberation and development." [Kuronov D. About the meaning layer in "Memory of the Road". 159 pp.].

We can cite many examples of this from the poet's lyrics. Cholpon reacts to the scenes of the period with his poetic heart in his poem "Leave me alone".

Эски дўстлар йўл адашиб ўлдилар,
Янги дўстлар бунинг учун кулдилар.
Янги йўлга оёқ босмай тўхтасам,
Бу йўлларда кутулишлик йўқ десам,
Сен ул чоқда қайси йўлга солардинг,
Фалокатдан қандай тортиб олардинг? [Чўлпон. Асарлар. Ж.1 47 б.]
Old friends lost their way and died,
And new friends laughed at this.
If I stop without stepping on a new path,
If I say that there is no way to escape,

What path did you take back then?

How would you recover from a disaster? [Cholpon. Works. C.1 47 p.]

The hesitations in the heart of the lyrical hero are penned in this poem,. The lyrical hero in it does not want to believe the literary-ideological lies of "new friends" who claimed to be a supporter of innovation. Because the lyrical "I" in the poem has a deep sense of the disaster that can happen, with a deep understanding that there is no salvation on this path. The real-life basis of the ideas in the poem is that the lyrical hero is looking for his own way in life, sometimes he hesitates about which way to go.

Чарчаган йўловчи йўлдан адашса,

Текис йўл қолса-да, тоғларни ошса,

Йўлни кўрсатқучи юлдуз-да қочса,

Шунда юпатгайми яланғоч чўллар?

Эркин далаларнинг эркин султони,

Сонсиз подаларнинг ёлғиз чўпони,

Най чолиб, тоғлардан истаса ёрни,

Балки юпатгуси “ёр” деган куйлар? [Чўлпон. Асарлар. Ж.1. 18 б.]

If a weary traveler goes astray,

Even if the road remains level, will he climb the mountains?

If the guiding star runs away,

Should bare deserts comfort him?

Free sultan of free fields,

Lonely shepherd of countless flocks,

He plays the flute and sings from the mountains,

Are songs about "beloved" soothing? [Cholpon. Works. C.1. 18 p.]

Tired of fighting for the future, lost on the way, to a wayfarer unable to find even a guiding star, the deserts and fields of his country seem comforting. The poet

thinks that the songs about his "beloved" were comforting to the one who was looking for his beloved among the mountains and rocks, turning into a shepherd in his love and playing the flute. In this case, the desire for freedom, the dream of freedom does not leave the lyrical hero, and without losing hope, he can find comfort and hope in every corner of the mother earth. In this, the images of the road and the traveler are directed to the expression of feelings related to a free and free life. The poem also poetically expresses the boundless feelings of patriotism. It seems that the poet's thoughts are logically continued in the poem "Way of Motherland":

Узоқ... оғир йўлга чиққан йўлчимен,
Бу йўлларда қилоғузим юлдуздир;
Мен юртимнинг пок истакли кучимен,
У юлдузнинг тугалиши кундуздир.

Томирларим олов каби қайнаган
Қонларини кечмишлардан олмишдир,
Билагимда ирғиб, чопиб ўйнаган,
Унутмаким, оёқларинг толмишдир.

Узоқ йўлнинг йўлчисимен, борамен,
Истагимни бу йўллардан оламен! [Чўлпон. Асарлар. Ж..1 23 б.]

I am a traveler on a long... difficult journey,
My brain is a star on these roads;
I am the pure desire of my country,
The end of this star is day.
My veins are boiling like fire
They took their blood from the past
jumping up and running on the wrist,

Forgetting that legs are tired.

I am a traveler of a long way, I will go,

I get what I want from these ways! [Cholpon. Works. C.1. 23 p.]

The lyrical hero calls himself the pure desire force of the country. Pure desire is undoubtedly the dream of freedom. The lyrical hero deeply feels that this path is difficult and long, but he never gives up and takes a step forward. On this way, his veins are boiling like fire, and even if his legs are tired, he will not give up his desire. The mental anguish he is suffering from causes him to be steadfast in his chosen path.

In general, the image of the road is used in Cholpon's poetry in a symbolic sense, expressing the poet's views on freedom and freedom. Undoubtedly, understanding the essence of this image will help us to understand the poet's spiritual feelings more deeply.

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issue 17, 2020

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